

TYPES AND FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF EDUCATIONAL TASKS IN LITERARY EDUCATION.

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Annotation. It is mentioned in the article the scientific-methodical literature of the developed countries of the world, literary education is directed mainly to work on the text, to read, understand and react to information presented in different ways. Special attention is paid to the level of usefulness of the information presented in each lesson for the student in everyday life, and questions, tasks and exercises are effectively used in the educational process.

Key words: teaching literature, state language, character, reader, essay, linguistic and technological aspects, genre.

Аннотация. В статье упоминается научно-методическая литература развитых стран мира, литературное образование направлено преимущественно на работу над текстом, на чтение, понимание и реагирование на информацию, преподносимую разными способами. Особое внимание уделяется уровню полезности информации, представленной на каждом уроке, для ученика в повседневной жизни, а вопросы, задания и упражнения эффективно используются в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: учебная литература, государственный язык, персонаж, читатель, эссе, лингвотехнологический аспекты, жанр.

In the experience of international language education, educational tasks are focused on effective communication. Educational assignments are formed on the basis of specific criteria, and in today's globalization conditions, literature is being integrated with other subjects and is being taught on the basis of new pedagogical

technologies. Interdisciplinary integration is certainly provided by questions and tasks, in this regard, the development of a system of pragmatic educational tasks should be noted as the main problem of the teaching methodology.

The methodology of teaching literature in the world uses the achievements of pedagogy and literary studies. Literature is a means of understanding existence for a person, the linguistic landscape of the world is formed in the student's thinking through fiction. "All peoples understand literature as the main criterion for national preservation, and while doing this through education, they pay great attention"¹ to the development of the skills of turning the reading of fiction into a national value and glorifying it. Today, one of the important issues is to discover new methods of teaching literature and to continuously introduce them into practice. Most of the countries are effectively using the achievements that are accepted as a model in the international teaching methodology. It is known from the observations that the development of comprehension and observation skills, preparation of the student for different speech situations are the main issues in the methodology of international literary education, and its implementation mainly depends on the quality and content of educational tasks. Educational content is revealed through educational tasks. Therefore, it is important to develop educational tasks for the student in the methodology of teaching literature.

In Uzbekistan, systematic work is being carried out to increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language and literature, and to introduce modern teaching methods. The new education system formed in the country also imposes necessary requirements on his education. "Each of us should regard attention to the state language as attention to independence, and respect and loyalty to the state language as respect and loyalty to the motherland, and make this view the rule of our lives" before mother tongue education, in particular, improvement of the scientific-methodical foundations of the development of educational tasks is an urgent task.

¹ uza.uz. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoevning o'zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilganining o'ttiz yilligiga bag'ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi nutqi. 2019 yil 21 oktyabr.

Integrating literature with language teaching in education, studying the work of art in historical, geographical, cultural, linguistic and technological aspects, basing on the dialogue between the author and the reader when working on the text, and the possibilities of interpretation and intertextual analysis are the world's leading scientific centers and universities educational institutions, including Arizona, Harvard, Michigan (USA), Cambridge, Oxford, Edinburgh (UK, Scotland), Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (Germany), University of Strasbourg (France), Seoul National University (Korea), Ankara Üniversitesi, Gazi Üniversitesi, Hacettepe University, Ondokuz Mayıs University (OMU) (Turkey), Moskovskii gosudarstvennyy pedagogicheskiy institute (Russia), Oñtustık Qazaqstan University named after M.Əuezov, L.N. Gumilyov named after y Eurasian National University (Kazakhstan), Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi (Uzbekistan) are conducting scientific research.

Teaching literature in connection with other types of art in the world education system, language learning through artistic texts, ways to motivate extensive reading, optimal approaches to identifying culture, history and traditions reflected in a literary text marked (Irem Nur Can, Esmā Tezcan, 2021); when studying works of different genres, strategies aimed at asking creativity-directing questions, writing background character descriptions of characters, and imagining the reader moving side by side with the hero have been determined (Linda Gajdusek, 1988); Through literary texts, the factors influencing the discovery of the hidden aspects of the way of life and thinking and culture of the peoples who speak different languages have been studied (Derwing, T., DeCorby, E. Ichikawa, J., & Jamieson, K., 1999) ; on the basis of cognitive approaches to artistic texts, a methodology was developed to find the socio-historical contexts of the event, use words in different angles, "smart exercises", and create imaginary conversations between the reader and the literary character (Ghosn, I., 2002); the importance of

literature in the development of communicative competence by applying linguistic knowledge in various social situations is highlighted (Guerrero, M.C., 2005); going beyond the surface meaning of the work, helping to get to its true essence, it is analyzed that the topic is considered an important element in the process of language learning (Mour, O.S., 2009); ways of developing reflective thinking in students by increasing the possibilities of using literary text have been researched (Abdollah Keshavarzi, 2012).

Implementation of the concept of modern literary education in the educational paradigm, where the main goal is to help students to feel the aesthetic essence of art, in particular, literature, to discover spiritual values, to improve artistic taste, and to help them to understand the text in depth. actual problems related to the increase have a special place. It takes into account the past and present experiences of the methodology of science during the period of independence. In the history of literary methodology, the first scientific attempts to teach it as a science were covered in the research works of S. Dolimov, Q. Ahmedov, N. Mallayev, A. Zunnunov, T. Boboyev. Later, Q. Yoldoshev, S. Matchonov, M. Mirgosimova, Q. Husanboyeva, R. Niyozmetova, U. Dolimov, V. Kadirov, Ye. Abduvalitov, Q. Yusupov, N. Yuldasheva, R. Keldiyorov, M. Tursunova updated pedagogical thinking in the experiences of Methodist scientists, organization of independent work, systematic approach to the analysis of artistic works, independent thinking and the role of problem-based education in this process, teaching of madrasahs and modernism, teaching of classic examples, folk oral creativity researched within the framework of problems such as comparative study, education of students in the spirit of patriotism, effective organization of literature classes.²

² Dolimov S., Ubaydullaev H., Ahmedov Q. Adabiyot o'qitish metodikasi. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1967. – 448 b.; Ahmedov Q. Hamza Hakimzodaning “Boy ila xizmatchi” dramasi o'rganish. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1968.; Mallaev N.M., Ismatov S.I. O'zbek adabiyoti tarixi. O'rta maktabning 9-sinfi uchun darslik. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1965; Boboev T. She'r ilmi ta'limi. – Toshkent, O'qituvchi, 1996; Zunnunov A., Hotamov N. Adabiyot nazariyasidan qo'llanma. O'rta maktablarning yuqori sinflari uchun. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1978.; Yo'ldoshev Q.B. Yangilangan pedagogik tafakkur va umumta'lim maktablarida adabiyot o'qitishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.

mainly in the teaching of literature on its characteristics as a work of art attention is paid to the pedagogical and psychological features of literature teaching by V. Kan-Kalik, V. I. Khazan, O. Yu. Bogdanova, V. G. Maransman, N. D. Moldavskaya, S. Kagan, A. B. Yesin, D. A. Mazilina, I. V. Ryzhkova, B. M. Eichenbaum, The problems of developing the competence of literary analysis in students are researched.⁴

Ped. fan. dok. ... diss. – Toshkent, 1997. – 306 b.; Matchonov S. Umumta'lim tizimida adabiyotdan mustaqil ishlarni tashkil etish. Ped. fan. dok. ... diss. – Toshkent, 1998. – 308 b.; Mirqosimova M.M. O'quvchilarda adabiy tahlil malakasini shakllantirish va takomillashtirish usullari. Ped. fan. dok. ... diss. – Toshkent, 1995. – 253 b.; Husanboeva Q.P. Adabiy ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarni mustaqil fikrlashga o'rgatishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari. Ped. fan. dok. ... diss. – Toshkent, 2006. – 34-b. – 262 b.; Niyozmetova R.X. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida o'zbek adabiyotini o'rganishning nazariy va metodik asoslari (rus guruhleri misolida). Ped. fan. dok. ... diss. – Toshkent, 2007. – 242 b.; Dolimov U. Jadid maktablar: ularda ona tili va adabiyot o'qitishning ilmiy-nazariy hamda amaliy asoslari. Ped. fan. dok. ... diss. avtoref. – Toshkent, 2008. – 44 b.; Keldiyorov R.A. Adabiyot darslari samaradorligini oshirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari (O'qituvchi kasbiy-ma'naviy fazilatlarini asosida). Ped. fan. nomz. ... diss. – Toshkent, 2001. – 137 b.; Abduvalitov Ye.B. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida qardosh xalqlar adabiyotini qiyosiy o'rganish (ta'lim o'zbek, qozoq, qirg'iz, qoraqalpoq va turkman tillarida olib boriladigan maktablarning V–IX sinflari adabiyot darslari misolida). Ped. fan. dok. (DSc) ... diss. – Toshkent, 2020. – 252 b.; Qodirov V. Umumta'lim maktablarida mumtoz adabiyot namunalari o'qitishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari. Ped. fan. dok. (DSc) ... diss. – Namangan, 2019. – 271 b.; Yusupov Q.A. Akademik litseylarda qoraqalpoq adabiyotini o'qitish metodikasi. Ped. fan. dok. (DSc) ... diss. avtoref. – Nukus, 2021. – 66 b.; Yuldasheva N.A. Adabiy ta'limda yoshlarni vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalashning ilmiy-metodik asoslari (umumiy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimi misolida). Ped. fan. dok. (DSc) ... diss. avtoref. – Chirchiq, 2022. – 65 b.; Tursunova M. Madrasalar ta'limida adabiyot o'qitish usullari. – Toshkent: MUMTOZ SO'Z, 2017. – 100 b.

³ Belenkiy G.I. Priobshenie k iskusstvu slova. – M.: Prosvetshenie, 1990. – 192 s.; Volkov F.I. Literatura kak vid xudojestvennogo tvorchestva. – Moskva: Prosvetshenie, 1985. – 128 s.; Domanskiy V.A. Literatura i kultura. Kulturologicheskiy podxod k izucheni. Slovestnosti v shkole. – M., 2002. – S. 82–91.; Kolokolsev Ye.N. Iskustvo na urokax literatury. – Kiev, 1991.; Kurilov A.S. Zachem i kakie uroki literatury nujny shkole? // Russkaya slovesnost. 2004. – № 5. – S. 6–10.; Lotman Yu.M. Ob iskusstve. – SPb., Iskustvo-SPb, 1998. – 794 s.; Cigaeva T.F. Vzaimodeystvie emotsionalno-obraznogo i logicheskogo nachal v chitatelskoy deyatel'nosti pyatiklassnika. Diss. ... kand. ped. nauk. – 1984. – 146 s.; Smelkova Z.S. Literatura kak vid isskustva. Kniga dlch uchitelya i uchashixsya. – M.: 1997. – 280 s.

⁴ Kan-Kalik V.A., Xazan V.I. Psixolo-pedagogicheskie osnovy prepodovaniya v shkole. – M.: Prosvetshenie, 1988. – 256 s.; Bogdanova O.Yu., Leonov S.A., Chertov V.F. Teoriya i metodika obucheniya literture. – M.: Akademiya, 2004. – 400 s.; Maransman Ye.K. Metodicheskaya sistema razvitiya obraznogo i konseptualnogo myshleniya shkolnikov v protsesse izucheniya literaturnykh proizvedeniy. Diss. ... dok. ped. nauk. – M., 2005. – 457 s.; Moldavskaya N.D. Literaturnoe razvitie shkolnikov v protsesse obucheniya. – M.: Pedagogika, 1976.; Kagan M.S. Chtenie kak fenomen kultury // izbrannyye trudy v 7 t. T. 3. Trudy po problemam teorii kultury. – SPb, 2008. – 717 s.; Yesin A.B. Printsipy i priemy analiza literaturnogo proizvedeniya. – M.: Flinta, Nauka, 2000. – 163 s.; Mazilina D.A. Ponyatie "avtorskaya pozitsiya" kak instrument analiza literaturnogo proizvedeniya v professionalnykh obrazovatelnykh organizatsiyax. Diss. ... kand. ped. nauk. – M., 2018. – 256 s.; Ryjkova I.V. Literaturnoe razvitie shkolnikov v protsesse dialoga chitatelya i pisatelya. Avtoref. diss. ... kand. ped. nauk. – SPb, 1998. – 21 s.; Eyxenbaum B.M. O printsipax izucheniya literatury v sredney shkole // Istoriya literaturnogo obrazovaniya v rossiyskoy shkole: xrestomatiya / avt.-sost. V.F.Chertov. – M.: 1999. – S. 290.

A. Arikan, Y. Cevdet (Turkey), C.J. Brumfit, R.A.Carter, M.N.Long, R.Walker from the point of view of associative-contextual approach to language teaching, communication, learning analysis by working on literature abroad , J. Collie, S. Slater, A. Maley, W.T. Littlewood (Great Britain); A. Kelly, S. MsKay, P. Minkoff (USA); It was studied by scientists such as M. Khatip, A.H. Rahimi (Iran).⁵

Study of local and foreign experiences of teaching literature, analysis and generalization of scientific and methodical views; comparative study of the compatibility of educational materials in textbooks with DTS and program requirements, identifying the causes of problems in literary education and proposing solutions; to study the current state of using educational tasks in the general secondary education system and to determine the place of pragmatic content educational tasks in literary education; improving the development of the content, methods and means of developing speaking skills and thinking skills through educational tasks; modernizing literary education, classifying the concepts of questions, exercises and tasks and their tasks, radically updating them, developing task samples;

⁵ Arikan, A. Student's evaluation of literature courses in the English language teacher education curriculum in Turkey. *Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*. 2005, 20. – P. 77–85; Brumfit, C.J. & Carter, R.A. *Literature and language teaching*. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1986; Carter, R. & Long, M.N. *Teaching Literature*. Harlow, Essex: Longman, 1991; Carter, R. Walker, R. & Brumfit, C. *Literature and the learner: methodological approach*. Modern English Publications and Classroom and the British Council; Collie, J. & Slater, S. *Literature in the Classroom* Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 1996; Littlewood W.T. *Literature in the school foreign-language course*. In C.J.Brumfit and R.A.Carter (ed.), *Literature and language teaching*. – Oxford: 1986. Oxford University Press. – P. 177– 83; Kelly, A., Collete (Ed). *Children's Literature: Discovery For A Life Time*. Arizona: Gorsuch Scarisbrick Publisher, 1996.; MsKay S. *Literature as content for ESL/EFL*. In M.CelceMurcia, *Teaching English as a second or foreign language*. – Boston, Heinle&Heinle, 2001; Minkoff P. *Talking it over class*. In A.Paran (ed.), *Literature in Language teaching and learning*. – Virginia, TESOL, 2006; Khatip, M. & Rahimi, A.H. *Literature and Language Teaching*. *Journal of Academic and Applied Studies*. Vol. 2 (6). Cambridge University Press, 2012. – P. 32–38; Maley, A. *Literature in the language classroom*. In R. Carter & D.Nunan (Eds.), *The Cambridge Guide to Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages*. Cambridge, 2001; Littlewood W.T. *Literature in the school foreign-language course*. In C.J.Brumfit and R.A.Carter (ed.), *Literature and language teaching*. – Oxford: 1986, Oxford University Press. – Pp. 177– 183; Yilmaz, Cevdet. *Introducing Literature to an EFL Classroom: Teacher's Instructional Methods and Student's Attitudes toward the Study of Literature*. www.ccsenet.org/elt www.ccsenet.org/elt. *English Language Teaching*. 2012. Vol. 5. – № 1.

to test the developed proposals and recommendations through experience in the content of textbooks, literature classes and to summarize the conclusions obtained. a new definition is given from a psychological and literary point of view, and their mutual difference, places of application, role and tasks in literary education are determined; in literary education, the use of exercises, mainly for the formation of skills and competences, the use of questions and assignments for the purpose of guiding the performance of an action, encouraging thinking and evaluating the acquired knowledge, skills and competences, the systematic formation of speech competence and it has been proven that development can be achieved; Creating questions and assignments for working with the text, asking questions to the interlocutor based on the speech situation in the development of speaking skills, the artistic-methodical levels for literary education were determined, and the scientific-methodical advantages of a pragmatic approach to question formulation in didactics were proven; along with the ability to read and understand based on the artistic text, the student can apply according to the communication situation, taking into account the need to develop speaking skills, recommendations were developed on the ways, types and innovative methods of teaching students to ask correct and logical questions; for the assessment system, being able to correctly understand what they heard by working on the text - (comprehension), being able to speak fluently and logically coherently based on the literary text - (speech), being able to read and understand the artistic text - (comprehension) and ability to write the text correctly and meaningfully - (essay) skills are improved taking into account the specific features of literary education. The current state of creating and using educational tasks in the process of literary education is analyzed, typical errors and shortcomings in textbooks and manuals are described, and the difficulties associated with a pragmatic approach to creating educational tasks in educational practice are described, and their elimination is given. the paths are shown; In literary education, the concepts of exercises, questions and tasks improved from a scientific and theoretical point of view are

given a new literary definition from the pedagogical, psychological and linguodidactic point of view, their mutual differences, places of application, their place in literary education and a system of using approaches to defining tasks in the creation of "Literature" textbooks has been developed; based on questions, exercises and examples of tasks created on the basis of classification and description of educational tasks, the ways of working on the text, reading comprehension, formation of speaking skills and independent work are described. The scientific value of the article is determined by the fact that it is monographically researched from the point of view of determining the place of educational tasks in literary education and reforming the content of education in improving the methodology of teaching literature. The practical significance of the research results in the creation of "Literature" textbooks, study guides, educational corpus, in the creation of science programs from the "Methodology of Teaching Literature" in the Uzbek language and literature education of higher educational institutions, philology faculties , material for the preparation of lecture texts, creation of manuals on the subject "Methodology of creating educational tasks" for master's courses on teaching Uzbek language and literature, 5-11 of general secondary schools - is explained by the fact that literature in classes serves as an important source for further improvement of teaching.

As a conclusion, it is impossible to say that it has been proven that the fundamental renewal of educational tasks in the literary education system is the basis for the modernization of "Literature" textbooks; in literary education, recommendations have been developed for creating questions and assignments for working with the text, for developing speaking skills, and for determining the literary and methodological levels of asking questions to the interlocutor based on the speech situation. It is explained by the relevance of the used research methods and scientific-theoretical information to official sources, the effectiveness of the presented analysis and experimental work is based on mathematical statistical methods, the implementation of conclusions, proposals and recommendations, and

the confirmation of the obtained results by authorized structures. by working on the artistic text according to the results of the experiment-test work - to be able to correctly understand what you heard - (comprehension), to be able to speak fluently and logically on the basis of the artistic text - (speech), to understand the artistic text The skills of being able to understand - (comprehension) and write an artistic text correctly and meaningfully - (essay) help to develop criteria for easy evaluation of results in literature education.

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